

New Quinazolone Congeners

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6,8-Substituted-2-(2-phenylethyl)-3-(1-methyl-2-phenylethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinones (2a-d) and 6,8-substituted-2-bromomethyl-3-(1-methyl-2-phenylethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinones (5a-d) were synthesised from 6,8-substituted-2-methyl-3-(1-methyl-2-phenylethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinones (1). Compounds 2 were further brominated and treated with secondary amines to yield 6,8-substituted-2-(2-phenyl-1,2-bis-substituted-ethyl)-3-(1-methyl-2-phenylethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinones (4a-g). Reaction of 5 with secondary amines afforded 6,8-substituted-(2-heterocyclyl methyl)-3-(1-methyl-2-phenylethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinones (6a-g).

QUINAZOLINONES are excellent reservoir of bioactive substances. A number of biological activities are associated with quinazolinones¹⁻⁴. The quinazolone function is quite stable and has inspired medicinal chemists to introduce this stable fragment on bioactive moieties to synthesise new potential medicinal agents. In the present study, *dl*- α -methylphenethylamine (amphetamine) has been incorporated at position-3 of quinazolinone to result 3-substituted quinazolinones which were further converted into 4a-g and 6a-g.

6,8-Substituted-2-methyl-3,1-benzoxazin-4(3H)-ones, synthesised by the reaction of anthranilic acids with acetic acid anhydride, on treatment with *dl*- α -methylphenethylamine afforded 6,8-substituted-2-methyl-3-(1-methyl-2-phenylethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinones (1a-d). Condensation of 1 with benzaldehyde yielded 2a-d which on bromination gave the respective dibromo derivatives (3a-d), which were further treated with secondary amines to yield 4a-g. Compounds 1 were also brominated to 6,8-substituted-2-bromomethyl-3-(1-methyl-2-phenylethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinones (5a-d) which on treatment with heterocyclic secondary amines yielded 6,8-substituted-2-(heterocyclylmethyl)-3-(1-methyl-2-phenylethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinones (6a-g) (Scheme 1).

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary and are uncorrected. The compounds were checked for their purity by tlc on silica gel G. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 Infracord spectrophotometer, pmr spectra on a Varian A 60D instrument using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a JMSD 300 double focussing spectrometer fitted with JMS 2000 data system with a source temperature of 180° at 3 kV acceleration voltage.

6,8-Substituted-2-methyl-3-(1-methyl-2-phenylethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinones (1a-d); 6,8-Substituted-2-methyl-3,1-benzoxazine-4(3H)-one (0.1 mol) was fused with *dl*- α -methylphenethylamine (0.1 mol). The fused mass was triturated with hot methanol.

Scheme 1

On cooling, the resulting solid was recrystallised from benzene/petroleum ether: 1a (X=Y=H) (70%), m.p. 175° (Found: N, 10.08. C₁₈H₁₈N₂O requires: N, 10.05%); δ (CDCl₃) 6.8-8.8 (9H, m, ArH), 3.4 (2H, d, CH₂ β -to NCO), 2.90 (1H, s, CH α -to NC=O), 2.05 (3H, s, C-CH₃) and 1.4-1.7 (3H, t, C-CH₃); [M]⁺ m/z 278; 1b (X=Br, Y=H) (65%), m.p. 168°; 1c (X=Y=Br) (60%), m.p. 195°; 1d (X=I, Y=H), (63%), m.p. 152°.

6,8-Substituted-3-(1-methyl-2-phenylethyl)-2-(2-phenylethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinones (2a-d): A mixture of 1 (0.05 mol), benzaldehyde (0.05 mol)

and traces of piperidine was fused on an oil-bath. The solid thus obtained was washed thoroughly with petroleum ether and crystallised from chloroform-petroleum ether: **2a** (62%), m.p. 143°; $\nu_{\max}$ 2900 (CH), 1680 (cyclic C=O) and 1600 cm^{-1} (C=C); δ (CDCl₃) 8.35 (1H, d, CH β -to C=N), 6.6–8.2 (14H, m, ArH), 6.3 (1H, d, CH α -to C=N), 3.5 (2H, d, CH₂Ar), 2.9 (1H, s, N-CH) and 1.9 (3H, s, C-CH₃); **2b** (56%), m.p. 130°; **2c** (55%), m.p. 231°; **2d** (65%), m.p. 112°.

6,8-Substituted-2-(1,2-dibromo-2-phenylethyl)-3-(1-methyl-2-phenylethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinones (3a-d): Bromine (0.1 mol) was added to a cooled solution of **2** in chloroform (60 ml) with continuous stirring. The reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature, the excess solvent distilled off and was cooled. The resulting solid was recrystallised from chloroform/petroleum ether.

2-(1,2-Dibromo-2-phenylethyl)-3-(1-methyl-3-phenylethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinone: 3a (59%), m.p. 100°; $\nu_{\max}$ 2920 (CH), 1685 (cyclic C=O) and 1580 cm^{-1} (C=N); **3b** (60%), m.p. 109°; **3c** (54%), m.p. 161°; **3d** (58%), m.p. 187°.

6,8-Substituted-2-(2-phenyl-1,2-bis-substituted-ethyl)-3-(1-methyl-2-phenylethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinones (4a-g): A mixture of **3** (0.01 mol) and arylamine (0.02 mol) in absolute alcohol (50 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. The residue obtained after removal of the solvent was poured into ice-cold water, and the resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from ethanol/water to yield the products (Table 1): **2-(1,2-di-4-morpholinyl)-2-phenylethyl)-3-(1-methyl-2-phenylethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinone, δ** (DMF) 8.6 (1H, d, CH, β -to C=N), 6.9–8.4 (14H, m, ArH), 6.1 (1H, d, α -to C=N), 3.2 (2H, d, CH₂Ar), 2.9–3.0 (1H, q, N-CH), 2.2–2.9 (16H, m, 8 $\times$ CH₂) and 2.0 (3H, s, C-CH₃); (M^+) m/z 538 and base peak m/z 330.

6,8-Substituted-2-(bromomethyl)-3-(1-methyl-2-phenylethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinones (5a-d): Bromine (0.1 mol) was added dropwise to a cooled solution of **1** in glacial acetic acid (100 ml) maintaining the temperature below 10°. Reaction mixture was refluxed for 4–5 h, then cooled and poured into NaOH solution (28 g in 150 ml of water). The resulting yellowish brown solid was dried and recrystallised from alcohol/water: **2-bromomethyl-3-(1-methyl-2-phenylethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinone (5a)**, 60%, m.p. 110°; **6-bromo-2-(bromomethyl)-3-(1-methyl-2-phenylethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinone (5b)**, m.p. 114°; **6,8-dibromo-2-(bromomethyl)-3-(1-methyl-2-phenylethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinone (5c)**, m.p. 147°; **6-iodo-2-(bromomethyl)-3-(1-methyl-2-phenylethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinone (5d)**, m.p. 105°.

6,8-Substituted-3-(1-methyl-2-phenylethyl)-2-(heterocyclylmethyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinones (6a-g): Compound **3** (0.01 mol) was added to an excess of

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4 AND 6*

Compd. no.**	X	Y	M.p. °C
4a	H	H	80
4b	Br	Br	90
4c	I	H	95
4d	H	H	105
4e	Br	H	127
4f	Br	Br	142
4g	I	H	152
6a	H	H	95
6b	Br	H	132
6c	Br	Br	210
6d	I	H	126
6e	H	H	115
6f	Br	Br	130
6g	I	H	166

*All compounds showed satisfactory elemental analyses and spectral data.

** and

for 4d-g 6e-g is

appropriate arylamine (0.05 mol) with continuous shaking. The reaction mixture was heated on a water-bath at 50–55° for 1 h and kept overnight at ambient temperature. The mixture was then poured into ice-cold water and the resulting solid was washed successively with aqueous sodium carbonate (1 *N*) and water. In some compounds a sticky mass was obtained which was extracted with ether, the ether layer was washed successively with sodium carbonate solution (1 *N*) and water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solvent was evaporated and crude solid recrystallised from methanol/water (Table 1): **6a** δ 7.5–8.4 (9H, m, ArH), 3.3 (2H, d, CH₂Ar), 3.1 (1H, q, C-H α -to NC=O), 2.8 (8H, m, 4 $\times$ CH₂), 2.05 (2H, s, -CH₂) and 1.9 (3H, CH₃); [M]⁺ m/z 363 and base peak m/z 329.

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